

ZURO

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UMTALI BOYS HIGH SCHOOL

FOREWORD.

How often it is one hears the cry of "it wasn't like this in my day", "our generation was more responsible than to-days", "if only we could live yesterday over again". This constant desire to return to the past can be seen in many forms: from the ridiculous, the aping of past clothing fashions, to the sublime a brilliant description of an historical event, and it is unlikely that one would find, no matter what generation or era, a radically different situation. Although the manifestation might change, the interest in the past remains constant.

Why is it that mankind, universally, finds itself spending time on examining time, time past, but not time forgotten? In attempting to answer the question, one steps immediately into the shoes of philosophers such as Plato, St. Augustine, Machiavelli, Hobbes, Marx and Nietzsche who have all in some aspect of their writings, attempted to pose an answer to the riddle of man's relationship to time and change. As can be imagined the answers given were widely divergent, from the idealism of Plato, the Christian hierarchy of St. Augustine to the material dialectic of Marx; and it is a clear example of man's striving for knowledge that these answers are frequently challenged and further answers given.

To-day not unnaturally, with the rapid advance of the medical sciences, some of the answers given are in psychological terms. Inherent in man's psychological make-up is an interest in the past, an interest which provides a sense of security, a sense of perspective and a sense of time. Security in that man finds a vague colouring of immortality from the never ending tale of his and his forefathers' struggles. Perspective from the depth and breadth of vision that the past affords him. And time, as all change is related to time and without time change would become meaningless.

Of more concern to schoolchildren, the educationalists have put forward their own ideas which provide the basis for the School's manifestation of an interest in the past - the study of History in the classroom. The ideas expressed all point to the practical value of yesterday for to-day. In annotating text books and answering historical problems, the pupils are presented with means by which their minds can be ordered and disciplined, while their appreciation of man's behaviour widened and given greater substance. Of pertinence to contemporary affairs, they are introduced to the workings of social, political and economic institutions which have their counterparts in the modern world. But perhaps most important of all, they are placed early in the role of arbiter, of politician, or statesman, of priest or Pope, of peasant or prince, and asked to analyse and then suggest answers to the type of problems that they will be required to answer as adults.

And thus it is that the Historical Society makes no apology for joining the ranks of those who would hark back to the past, for it accepts as fundamental that the past is of vital relevance to the present and future, and as its contribution to the development of the relationship between the past and present, it presents and hopes to present annually, ZURO, a magazine of historical information, recording the activities of the Society during the course of the year. In so doing it hopes to provide the channel by which yesterday (Zuro is the Shona word for yesterday) becomes meaningful for to-day.

B.DAVIDGE.

MINUTES OF MEETINGS HELD BY THE HISTORY SOCIETY.

8th March, 1968.

Speakers : Messrs. Hulley and Coleman and Miss Maritz.

General Topic : "Early History of our School."

First to speak was Mr. C. Hulley. Mr. Hulley who had arrived in Umtali (Old Umtali) in 1895, spoke on the first school established in the district in March, 1896. He stated that the school was held in a pole and dagga hut, furnished with packing cases for desks. Miss Zillah Miles (later Mrs. Dick Tulloch) had offered to teach the children, of which there were approximately a dozen. He also stated that the first school team ever to be formed was a soccer team. Mr. Hulley then mentioned the school which was founded by the American Methodist Episcopal Mission (this was established in 1898 under the name of the "Umtali Academy"): he continued by saying that some of the teachers at the school were very good while others tended to be indifferent. He then went on to tell of the formation of another school under the auspices of the Church of England at St. John's Church in 1904; this school was under the charge of Rev. Roberts, an excellent disciplinarian. Another teacher at this school was Mrs. Hugh Tulloch (nee Rosa St. Clair) who had tutored Kingsley Fairbridge, and who was according to Mr. Hulley a very knowledgeable teacher and a skilful dramatist. Mr. Hulley, who later attended several schools in Salisbury, ended by saying some masters at that period were "monsters" while others could not even "read or write."

Miss Maritz, who has had a long association with Umtali Schools, first as pupil from 1915 to 1926, then as Bursar at the Umtali High School (present Umtali Girls' High School) and later as Bursar of Umtali Boys' High School from 1954 to 1962 spoke next. Miss Maritz talked generally on the educational facilities which were available in the early days when she was at school. She then explained the system of examinations which existed in her days of schooling. These were she stated, the Junior Certificate and Matriculation (which was written by Standard VII pupils - approximately when the pupils were 16); she also elaborated on the Beit Scholarships which were started while she was at school. Miss Maritz then spoke briefly on sport or rather the lack of it and continuing, stated that the first hostel (of Umtali High School) consisted of rented houses in Darlington (Ross Avenue). She then went on to speak of other hostel developments up to 1924 when Chancellor House, a hostel for boys, was opened. She ended by discussing the opening of the new school (the present Umtali Girls' High School - the Umtali High School had been previously at the old Junior School) in 1926 by the Earl of Athlone.

Last to speak was Mr. A.W.H. Coleman, an ex-pupil (attended school from 1921 - 1929), who is well known in Umtali schooling circles. He stated that before Mr. Livingston's era there was no true school organisation, e.g. no games and it was Mr. Livingston who became Head in 1922 that really welded the school into a real machine. He provided the school with a proper uniform in 1923 and adequate sporting amenities. He also explained that co-education supplied no disadvantages but led to academic rivalry between the sexes which improved standards of work; he added that the girls' discipline was much sterner in those days. Mr. Coleman continued by stating that the first rugby ground was built where Athlone Hostel now stands - the schoolboys helped in its construction. He then recounted that one of the favourite weekend pastimes of cadets was to borrow a rifle and a few rounds from the school armoury and go hunting up at Tiger Kloof. Mr. Coleman put forward that the standard of education then was as good as that of to-day - only methods have changed. Mr. Coleman ended by briefly talking about the Old Borderers' Association of which he is a prominent member.

17th May, 1968.

Speaker : Mr. Bernhard.

Topic : Archaeology.

Mr. Bernhard opened by relating that archaeology is no longer the hobby of a crank or a treasure hunting affair but an exact science. Basically archaeology included in its studies the History of Man. He outlined the various Ages e.g. Stone and Iron Ages and the ethnography of these periods with special relation to Rhodesia. He said that in this day and age to be a successful archaeologist one must have the combined knowledge of a geographer and an anthropologist for the correct interpretation of results. Mr. Bernhard then went on to talk of the evidence in the form of pottery and various other implements which remain as proof of the various races which were at one time either settlers or squatters in the early history of Rhodesia.

Mr. Bernhard particularly referred to Rhodesia's great archaeological site - Zimbabwe - and its origins. Coming closer to home he elaborated on his own finds while excavating at Murehwa's Hill and remarked upon the Inyanga ruins. In closing he touched on archaeological techniques and how they vary from country to country. He gave an example by saying methods of excavation in Rhodesia would differ from those used in Egypt and in Europe.

He praised and also explained the methods of carbon 14 dating and lastly mentioned his hopes for further valuable finds at Murehwa.

26th July, 1968.

Speaker : Mrs. Tindall.

Topic : The Great Zimbabwe Myth.

Mrs. Tindall began by stating there were three main questions facing those who chose to investigate the myth surrounding Zimbabwe. What is Zimbabwe? Who built it? When? According to Mrs. Tindall the best piece of literature on these subjects is Sumner's "Zimbabwe: a Rhodesian Mystery" - early literature contained too many romantic theories. She then continued discussing the two main methods of dating: the first method by noting the dates of imported articles and the second by carbon 14 dating. On the archaeological excavations Mrs. Tindall said the most important were those by Messrs. Summers, Whitty and Robinson in 1958 while she regretted the havoc wrought by the gold seeking Hall in 1902: he left no records of his work and removed a great deal of valuable material from the Great Enclosure. Mrs. Tindall also remarked on the work carried out by MacIver in 1950 and Gertrude Caton-Thompson in 1929. Mrs. Tindall then referred back to the 1958 excavations during which Robinson while working at the Acropolis had succeeded in forming the pottery found there into five successive and differing types; at the same time Whitty formulated a comprehensive classification of walling styles while Summers through his work established a sequence of building events at Zimbabwe.

Mrs. Tindall then critically examined the importance of Zimbabwe as an economic, religious and political centre, in the light of artifacts such as imported pottery, soapstone birds and divining bowls, and gold plated ornaments which have been found at the Ruins.

In concluding her talk, Mrs. Tindall discussed the question of who built Zimbabwe. She said early buildings were erected approximately during the 11th century and that she had two theories as to who built the ruins. Her first suggestion as to the identity of the builders was the indigenous people; in her second theory she proposed that the Ruins could have been constructed by Indonesians or people from what is now Madagascar - both races commemorated their chiefs by making pillars similar to those found at Zimbabwe. This ended a most interesting talk.

MINUTES OF LECTURES HELD BY THE UMTALI MUSEUM SOCIETY AND
WHICH WERE ATTENDED BY HISTORY SOCIETY MEMBERS.

23rd February, 1968.

Speaker : Professor Gelfand of the University College of Rhodesia.
Topic : "Shona Religion."

This talk, on a subject that is not widely known throughout Rhodesia, was very informative and enlightening. Professor Gelfand explained that the Shona believed in a God or Mwari, "creator of all, good and evil." Mwari was approached by the people through a number of intermediaries. He then spoke of the various spirits which exist in the Shona Religion: the Mhondoro or tribal spirit, the Mudzimu or family spirits, the Shave or the alien spirit. He stated that the "pillar of Shona Religion is the medium (or swikiro). Shona religion is a form of spiritualism." He then elaborated on the functions of the mediums. He also referred to the Ngangas - the true witch doctors and the Varoyi the evil witch doctors. Professor Gelfand in closing discussed the part Shona Religion plays in the life of the modern day African.

5th April, 1968.

Speaker : Mr. Warhurst, Head of the Department of History at the
University College of Rhodesia.
Topic : "Establishment of the Eastern Boundary 1890 - 1900."

Mr. Warhurst opened his talk by speaking on the activities of the Portuguese in and around Manicaland since the 15th century and up to the 19th century. In the 19th century the Portuguese exercised a rather shadowy administration over the area. This depended on a number of powerful individuals such as Gouveia, a Portuguese prazo-holder who claimed that the Chief of the Manica had accepted his authority; another Chief Gungunyana, whose territory ran from the Sabi to the Mocambique coast, was claimed to hold a Portuguese administrative title. In the 1880's Major Paiva d'Ardrada attempted to increase Portuguese influence in the interior by means of the 'Companhia da Mocambique.' However when the Column (Pioneer) entered Rhodesia, Rhodes desired Manica for its gold and Gungunhana's territory (Gaza) for a route to the sea. Colquhoun was dispatched from the Column to obtain a concession in favour of the B.S.A. Co. from Mutasa. This he duly achieved on the 14th September. Mutasa denied Portuguese dependence. However according to Mr. Warhurst, a number of Portuguese leaders attempted to reaffirm Portuguese claims - they were arrested by Forbes (Captain in B.S.A.Co. forces) who then pressed on to try and capture Beira - unfortunately he was recalled. A temporary agreement was reached by the British and Portuguese Governments in Nov. 1890. However, the B.S.A.Co. hung on to Manica and the Portuguese made subsequent attacks on Company forces in Manica - they were successfully repelled. However, Company attempts to obtain Gaza were thwarted by the British Prime Minister, Lord Salisbury, who did not wish to antagonise the Portuguese. By the Anglo-Portuguese Treaty of August, 1891 the permanent eastern boundary was laid down.

M.DAVIDSON.
Secretary.

THE SCHOOL'S GENESIS, 1896 - 1909.

Everything must have its beginning or the first brick in its House of History. Where our school was concerned, it was the advent of Miss Zillah Miles in Umtali (Old Umtali).

According to the census of 1895, the total population of Umtali and surrounding districts was 341; this consisted of 272 men, 33 women and 36 children all under the age of 12.¹ However, as yet there were no educational facilities provided for these children and this blemish was a growing source of anxiety for the parents of Umtali. Miss Miles (later Mrs. Dick Tulloch) arrived in Umtali in December, 1895 coming via Beira (a very arduous journey in those days) accompanied by her brother. It soon became known that Miss Miles had gained experience as a private teacher in England and loved children; she was approached by parents and asked to open a school. She willingly accepted this task and she sums everything up by saying "everything was new and strange, but everyone was filled with great hopes for the future."²

Subsequently the first school was started in a meagre pole and dagga hut in March, 1896. Miss Miles describes the hut as being "big enough for present purposes, though it was not in the best state of preservation, a coat of white-wash inside and a little extra thatch outside made it possible."³ Trestles and planks, a couple of nails, led to a few tables, while packing cases were provided for chairs.

A small map was attached to one of the mud walls and a 2 ft. square window was covered with a piece of calico. While outside attached to a reed, stuck in the thatch, there fluttered a small Union Jack - the school was ready for its pupils. A few text books were "collected from the dusty corners of Umtali."⁴ The first schoolday arrived and Miss Miles found waiting for her "a small band of a dozen pupils all eager, all expectant and some of them a wee bit scared as to the outcome of this very new experience but perhaps, had they but known it, hardly more scared than their teacher."⁵ Miss Miles "felt it to be a great undertaking to be responsible for the instilling of right principles and as much knowledge as possible into their hearts and brains."⁶ On the first day the pupils and the teacher made "rules and regulations and formed mutual resolutions to make the school one of the best"⁷. The scholars possessed a total of 2 slates between them and the school hours were set down as being from 8.30 - 12.30 a.m. Exercise books had to be made from trimmings left over from the Rhodesia Advertiser (later Umtali Post). Shortage of paper was not uncommon

1. Rhodesia Advertiser 1895, National Archives.
2. School Magazine, 1929.
3. School Magazine, 1929.
4. School Magazine, 1929.
5. Pioneering Women by J. Boggie.
6. School Magazine, 1929.
7. School Magazine, 1929.

Miss Miles recounts an old pioneer lady telling her the surprise expressed by her parents in England when she sent them a letter written on a piece of old sandpaper. During the Matabele and Mashona Rebellion, Miss Miles remembers that, if the local chief of the Manica, Mutasa rose, a rocket was to be fired to warn the local populace. However on occasions a rocket was fired as a practice and several times after the event people rushed into the laager terrified and absolutely exhausted fearing that Mutasa had risen. After having turned up in "non-descript costumes" and having learned the truth they returned home in not a "very angelic frame of mind." ¹ Fortunately the school was situated near the laager which was only three minutes walk away - work there continued. On 6th January, 1897 the first school sports were held.

Mr. C. Hulley, one of Miss Miles's early pupils, remembers her as being a very good teacher. He also related that Miss Miles kept a "dunce" cap, which was in reality a large girl's hat; on one occasion Mr. Hulley's brother misbehaved in class and was asked to don the dunce cap. Rather than face humiliation he jumped out of the window and ran away.

Towards the end of 1897 Umtali began to move to form the rail head for the coming railway. The High Commissioner, Sir Alfred Milner came out to review the present site in November, 1897 and while in Umtali he had an interview with Miss Miles. As a result he promised Miss Miles, government (then the British South Africa Co.) grants for furniture and for each individual pupil. When the school moved to the present site of Umtali, the government made available a wood and iron office, also moved from the old site, for the school (this was erected as far as can be ascertained near Kopje House which was then the hospital). At this time the approximate number of pupils was 27; who each paid a guinea a term.

Up till 1898 this school, which was a private school, was the only school in Umtali. However, in August, 1898 a meeting of interested parties convened to discuss the question of the foundation of a town school. The meeting was held in the Court House, Major Turner taking the chair, those present included a number of Umtali's leading citizens. It was agreed to use a corner of the Government building for the school. The gathering also decided upon a school management board of which the Resident Magistrate would be chairman. Miss Miles's school had become inadequate.

In September of the same year, the Rev. and Mrs. Morris Ehnes, sailed from the United States of America to take up the post of Head of the School. The Ehnes were both college graduates and were to work under the auspices of the American Methodist Episcopal Church. The Church was sending out also school furniture and all other educational needs, including musical instruments. Rev. Ehnes duly arrived in Umtali. In October another meeting was held in the court to hear proposals put forward by the Rev. Ehnes. The missionary outlined his plans for the school - he had decided that there would be a daily reading from the Bible but no other religious training.

1. Pioneering Women by J. Boggie.

On 21st November, 1898 the new school was opened. Children of five years and upwards could be taught all the common branches of education, such as arithmetic, penmanship, reading, art, geography, history and grammar. The mission could also cater for pupils wishing to pursue higher studies.

By the turn of the century the school, now known as the 'Umtali Academy' or the 'Umtali Public School' was firmly established. It boasted of 32 pupils and 2 teachers. The Government realised the importance of the school and the school was brought under the British South Africa Company's Education Ordinance - by this religion was to be taught during school hours, grants were to be given for the teaching of additional subjects, and the government was to pay for school expenses, including teachers' wages.¹ The first school concert ever held took place during this year. It was arranged by Mr. & Mrs. Ehnes and Mrs. Hugh Tulloch (Rosa St. Clair) and consisted of a number of songs and the portrayal of a scenic poem.

Mr. Ehnes commenting on the work at Umtali Public School in 1900 stated that he had "had considerable difficulties in arranging the school during the past period, through the delay and loss of books on the way to Umtali; the bad attendance of some of the pupils and the lack of room."² It was also announced that in 1901 the school would move to new buildings and it was hoped to gain a third teacher and start evening classes.

The location of the new school was excellent, the building had first started construction under the name of the "Goldfields Hotel" but had been taken over by the American Mission, completed and now formed the new 'Umtali Academy'. The building, a double storey was admirably arranged for school, resident teachers and for boarding accommodation for pupils. Evening classes were started and had an average attendance of 3. However the number of pupils had dropped to 31 - this total comprised 16 boys and 15 girls. During 1901 the school received its first government grant which amounted to £323.8.6d. this was to be used for rent, teachers' half salaries, evening school and various requisites. The Report of the Director of Education pointed out some very interesting facts worth printing: in 1901 there were 8 government aided schools, with a total of 433 pupils and 23 teachers; the number of pupils per teacher was 18.8 The 'Umtali Academy' was among the first schools started in Rhodesia.

On a visit in 1902 to the school, Mr. Duthie, a supervising inspector, later Director of Education praised the school - by then the sum of the pupils had risen to 48. In the course of the same year the Rev. Emory Beetham replaced Rev. Ehnes as principal and under him the school moved on handsomely receiving full interest from the pupils as well as full attendance. As far as can be ascertained the Rev. Beetham was a most conscientious principal and went to great

1. Director of Education's Report, National Archives.
2. Umtali Post - then Rhodesia Advertiser, 1900, National Archives.

extremes to receive government help to educate the children of financially poor parents. While he was desperately trying to acquire money for the above purpose, he kept the children on at the school¹ on the grounds of hope. In one letter to the Education Department he stated "At the present there seems to be no other course open to us but to deprive the poor of the privilege of education!" In 1903 he was granted an Indigent Children Grant worth £40,10s. In 1902 to help the Church pay for the building (the x Goldfields Hotel) which it had purchased to form the school, it was loaned £2,800. by the Government.

In 1904 there were 52 pupils regularly attending the school. the first official record of the school being commended for its work in a specific sphere can be found when Mr. Duthie, the Director of Education noted the school for its work in nature study! It was around 1904 that the Boys' Brigade was first started in Umtali, it is also thought that the first school team was formed during this period - a soccer team, which had one unusual feature; it had no captain - all the members of the team in a vote for captaincy had elected themselves to the position; it was then considered wise to leave the post of captain vacant.

In the beginning of 1905 the Rev. Beetham left and was succeeded by the Rev. James E. Ferris. Due to the departure of Rev. Beetham and the fact that parents had become uncomfortable at hearing the American accents their children were picking up from their American teachers, the Anglican Church decided to come into her own, and form the Umtali High School, which was held at the old St. John's Church.

In April, 1905 a meeting was held in the Court House for the purpose of electing a Board of Management for the new school.

The Rev. Arthur Robins was in charge of the school and was assisted by Mrs. Hugh Tulloch (Rosa St. Clair) the lessons were held behind the altar which was curtained off. Rev. Robins was a strict disciplinarian; he was reputed to have a clicker, on entering the class, the pupils would stand up at his first click, say good morning to him on the second and greet Mrs. Tulloch on the third. It was Rev. Robins and Mrs. Tulloch who tutored Kingsley Fairbridge and helped him to gain entrance to Oxford. Kingsley Fairbridge held a great regard for Mrs. Tulloch and later wrote a poem in honour of her - "Earning thy living with thy brain and hand,
Yet finding time to share they dauntless heart
With all who need,
Thy culture with the uncultured:
Sowing seed,
Whereof the hargest is not thine . . . "

However the Government at this stage did not altogether approve of a second school in Umtali and were not prepared to aid. Fortunately the Rhodes Trustees came to the rescue with a grant to the new school, which was named the Umtali High School - the Trustees believed the educational facilities in Umtali to be of an unsatisfactory nature. The Trustees emphatically stated they did not intend to assist the Umtali High School purely to oppose the Umtali Public School that was run by the Government.

In 1906 due to the opening of the Umtali High School the number of pupils at the Umtali Public School had dropped to 49, they were taught by a total of 5 teachers. Two of these were pupil teachers who not only had to teach during the whole school day but also had to take lessons in the afternoons and then had to study for their final examinations, which would establish them as full-time teachers. During the course of the same year, in August, the Umtali High School had made such progress that the Administrator of Southern Rhodesia felt the government could no longer ignore the school. The School was brought under the Educational Ordinance of 1899 and received a temporary and provisional grant to the value of £145.¹

By 1907 the Umtali High School consisted of 27 scholars and 3 teachers compared with the Umtali Public School which had 49 students and 5 teachers.² Several interesting factors appeared in the Inspector's Report of September, 1907.³ It showed that average age of pupils in Standard I of the Umtali Public School was 9.8 years - 2 years above average! The same report stated "a lack of discipline" at the Umtali Public School "was evident" and "would account for inefficient work." However, the cause of this was the large number of Dutch speaking children, with little educational background, who had recently joined the school. Mrs. Mayo (nee Blezer) who was a student teacher during this period noted that the American Mission was gradually lessening its interest in the school. Mr. Ferris had now decided to devote all his time to missionary work and in September, 1907 Mrs. Robson became the new head.

The schools gradually were increasing in number and by 1908 the Umtali Public School had 70 pupils compared with the Umtali High School which had 25 scholars. Basically the schooling system of this period was as follows: one started in the kindergarten department of the school which consisted of sub-standards A and B, a pupil then went on to the higher school with standards ranging from I - VII. In standard V a pupil wrote the Junior Certificate examination while in Standard VI the Beit examination was written (Beit scholarships and grants had been introduced during the course of this year) and finally in Standard VII the university entrance examination - Matriculation - was written.

The Inspector's report of August, 1908 described Standard IV of the Umtali Public School as being "mostly a backward and unintelligent lot" - this was again due to a large influx of Dutch children.

Nevertheless it seemed a pity to have two small schools in Umtali rather than one large school. Consequently in 1908 careful attention was paid to the question of amalgamation. When the parents of the scholars obtained wind of the proposed amalgamation of the two schools into a Government aided undenominational school, a new problem arose and a great deal of letter writing took place between the School Advisory Committee of Umtali Public School and the Director of Education, Mr. Duthie. The

1. Director of Education - Report, National Archives.
2. Director of Education - Report, Umtali Girls' High School Archives.
3. National Archives.

The difficulty concerned the appointment of members to the committee for the new school. The Umtali public disagreed with the government proposal that the Sanitary Board should elect members to the committee. The public argued that none of the Board members had children at either of the schools. Eventually after much wrangling, it was agreed that the members to the School Advisory Committee should be elected at a public meeting. Five members were elected and approved by the Administrator of Rhodesia, they were:- Dr. Harper, Messrs. English, Laing, Snashall and Hosgood. The amalgamation had received valuable support from the Bishop of Africa for the American Methodist Episcopal Church, Mr. Joseph Hartzell, who said in a letter to the Education Department: "You know from the first I believed in public schools, that is, the country taking the entire responsibility. Our relations have been pleasant and good work has been done. But now with everything under your own control and more money and people, better work than ever will be accomplished." The date of amalgamation was set for January, 1909.

Meanwhile in October, 1908 Mr. Garner, from Belfast, Ireland became Head of the Umtali Public School in place of Mr. Robson. According to an Inspector's Report in 1908². Mr. Garner had "improved the discipline and cleanliness of the pupils" which had up till now been of a low standard.

With the approaching amalgamation on the horizon the scholars' parents requested that Mr. Garner and his staff should retain their positions at the new school to be opened. In January, 1909 the new amalgamated government school opened under the headship of Mr. Garner. The government had purchased the American Methodist School building for a total of £2,802.15s.4d. (this price included additions and repairs.) There was a total of 117 pupils and 5 teachers attending the school. The Government further purchased furniture and requisites from the Umtali Public School and Umtali High School for £439.14s.4d.³. The new school was to be known as the Umtali Public School.

Some interesting facts are shown by the following distribution tables for the new school.

Pupils' Ages	Under 5	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15 & over
Nos. in age groups	10	3	11	12	13	14	12	11	11	7	7	6

The following is a table to show the number of pupils in the various standards in the year 1909

Standards	VII	VI	V	IV	III	II	I	Below I
No. of pupils	-	8	7	9	15	16	22	40

After developing from a private school and the two Church Schools into the Umtali Public School in 1909, the school never looked back and rapidly developed. So much so, that in 1926 the school was moved to new buildings (the present Umtali Girls' High School) and even this later became inadequate: in 1954 the up till then co-educational school broke up into separate schools for boys and girls, the present Umtali Boys' High School and Umtali Girls' High School of to-day.

M.DAVIDSON, VIM.

1. National Archives.
2. National Archives.
3. Director of Education's Report, Umtali Girls' High School Archives.

ZIWA.

On Sunday, 2nd June nine members of the History Society went on an expedition to Ziwa in Inyanga. The expedition was divided into two sections, the first of which was a visit to the Nyahokwe Field Museum and the Ancient Village Site.

The Museum shows the cultural remains of the inhabitants of the area from Stone Age Man, some 40,000 years ago up to the ancestors of the present Bantu-speaking people. Articles displayed included a large amount of pottery, beads and iron and stone tools and weapons. It was interesting to find that the dates given in the descriptions near the display cases obtained from charcoal samples were not only measured at the University College in Salisbury but also at Berne University, Switzerland.

Leaving the museum we followed a path up Nyahokwe Hill. Beside this path was a series of pits and other buildings. A controversy surrounds these pits in that some people think that they were used by humans while others think that they were built to house animals.

One of the most striking features about Nyahokwe Hill is that it is terraced from top to bottom. It is thought that some form of agriculture was carried out on these artificially made terraces.

After crossing an area of bare granite we reached the remains of the village site. The first enclosure includes the seats of the dari, "the meeting place of the elders of the district." Adjoining this there are a number of pits.

Further up the hillside are the remains of the main village. This has lintled entrances, passages and a series of niches in the outside walls.

After examining some rock paintings on the other side of the hill, we returned to the museum and from there set out to find a second collection of rock paintings. We were, however, unable to find them and so returned to the museum.

After lunch we went to see a reconstruction of a smelting furnace. These furnaces were used for smelting iron by the Ziwa peoples and the one we saw was an example of one of three types known to have been used locally.

Leaving Nyahokwe we made our way to the Van Niekerk Ruins. The examination of these made up the second section of the expedition. These ruins cover a very large area and at one time a great number of people must have lived here. The grass covering these ruins had been only partly cleared.

On sloping ground we found terraces similar to those at Nyahokwe.

We finished our tour of these ruins by visiting a small fort situated on the highest land in the area, and returned to Umtali having had an enjoyable and interesting time.

G.MCEWAN, C.I.

ZIMBABWE, 1968.

Although the weather at Zimbabwe when we arrived left much to be desired, being cold and damp, the tents were finally put up after a bit of a struggle, and some sort of fire appeared, over which the first meal consisting of steak and potatoes was cooked. As had been decided, the cooking was left to the girls and Mrs. Griffiths, assisted most of the time by Mr. Davidge, while the general washing up and making of fires was assigned to the boys.

The first evening passed pleasantly with the group singing to the accompaniment of an accordion. Then we retired to ice-cold sleeping bags in which to spend a rather sleepless night. The following morning, the weather being no better, we breakfasted on uncooked porridge, delicately flavoured with paraffin, which eventually found its way by devious routes to the dustbin, followed by eggs, bacon and coffee. Fortunately, as we had camped next to a thatched shelter the food could be kept dry, and we had a convenient place to prepare meals.

After a morning up the Acropolis, we lunched on cold meat and salad, and then went off to explore the valley ruins. That night, the weather having at last cleared up, we sat round the fire to eat a meal of stew and bread. The evening passed as the one before, in singing songs. Monday morning saw us up bright and early, and after a breakfast of corn fritters we divided into two groups, one of which went to visit the museum and Karanga village while the others stayed in camp. At midday we took a picnic lunch to Lake Kyle, returning early so that the other group could visit the museum. Supper that night consisted of roast meat, but either the meal or something else seemed to have had an adverse effect on the singing, so most of the group retired early. Tuesday morning was spent in preparing for our return.

The return journey was made without incident, though car-sickness was experienced for the first time on the trip. We arrived back at Kopje shortly after 5 o'clock and soon disembarked after a tiring but interesting weekend.

C.MURRAY. U VI.

THE KARANGA VILLAGE AND SOCIETY AS
SEEN AT ZIMBABWE.

Basically the Karanga Village on view at Zimbabwe consisted of a family hut, a girl's hut (nanga) and a bachelor's hut (gota), grain bins (dura), a chicken coup, a hut containing the body of a dead chief, a nganga's (witch-doctor) hut and a hut to illustrate methods of construction. Also on sight was a furnace, a threshing area, an exhibit on pottery making and a dure, a place solely for men, where they worked, gossiped and ate.

The huts were built with wattle poles and daga (wind and water proof) the interior walls being smooth, the floors of the huts had been smeared with manure, which forms a hard flat surface (keeps out ants). Generally in the middle of the huts the fire area could be found. Of the pottery in evidence, all of which is modern were various pots, the Chirongo for water, the Mbidziro for beer, and the Shambakodzi for cooking. These pots are made by the women, without the aid of a potter's wheel. On the hut floors were sleeping mats made either of canes or rushes - adjacent to the father's mats were his weapons (one was not safe at any time). On the hut floors, and walls could be found wooden plates, spoons, porridge sticks, pestles and mortars (for grinding tobacco as well as millet) and many other implements for rudimentary farming, e.g. hoes. Various baskets and bark sacks were on show as were toys in boys' and girls' huts and various ornaments e.g. representing fertility. In several huts were found chikwa (pot stands) chitukwiro (raised dais for husband) and zwipanda (shelves). In the hut of the nganga, his numerous wares were displayed - herbs, horns, musical implements and his hakata (throwing bones - consisted of four types, totalling six, bones with two identical pairs) and also his divining bowl (this is used by floating seeds in water in the bowl and reading the message from the symbols on the bowl where the seed touches the rim).

The most interesting feature of the village was a hut which contained the body of a dead chief. When a chief dies and decomposition has set in, his body is wrapped in a fresh black ox-hide and placed in a specially constructed hut (chiwumba) on a platform. This hut is carefully sealed so that the spirit of the departed chief may not escape (it cannot escape through the door due to the fact it cannot retreat via the way it came). The blisters which form on the corpse are regularly punctured, the fluid being collected in a pot, as are the maggots extracted from the body - this pot is buried with the chief its contents are supposed to contain part of the chief's spirit. The wives of the dead chief keep a constant watch on the corpse and a fire is continuously burnt along with meat to please the spirit and no doubt to overcome the smell. When the corpse is dried out, a hole is knocked out of the right hand side of the hut (to allow the spirit to follow the body), normally opposite the door, the chief is then removed and buried with elaborate ceremony.

The social structure of the Karanga is based on, in order of importance, the chief, the council (wa-chinda) the nganga and rainmaker, the headmen, Royal wives, Matrons and Mother-in-laws, the male, female and lastly the children. The chief is the ruling body of the tribe and is advised by the council which is comprised of prominent headmen, royal spirit mediums and part official historians - the function of the council is to voice the will of ancestral kings and maintain tribal traditions. The nganga - who is distinguishable from the muroyi (sorcerer) has tremendous influence on the social life of the tribe and

is an honoured person. The nganga is mainly a herbalist, diviner and exorcist.

The tribal people are basically exogamous, patrilineal clans which are totemic. Marriage in the clans used to be polygamous and involved the payment of lobolas. Normally the law of succession for chieftancy is for the first born son to succeed, if there are no sons it goes from brother to brother or to son of eldest brother.

In Karanga Society there exists three types of crime, (a) Crime against the State e.g. witchcraft - punishment usually banishment; (b) Crime against person e.g. adultery, incest, treason - punishment death; (c) Crime against property, e.g. trespassing on cultivation and grazing rights, arson - punishment payment of cattle made, theft - if the thief was nocturnal - death if habitual - hands severed.

With trials into the unknown e.g. evil witchcraft, the accused party had to undergo a "boiling water" or "emetic" test to assess guilt or innocence. However the final verdict was always to be given by the chief.

The Karanga family is a self-contained economic unit, usually with the father at its head. Each sex in the family has a specific job of work to do. The husband constructs the hut leaving a zwipanda (shelf) and a goni (a little door) as well as the dura (grain bin). He also manufactures bark sacks, baskets, sleeping mats (from canes or rushes), stools, head rests, farm implements and cooking utensils. The husband also dries and softens animal skins and uses them for making clothing e.g. wife's shashiko. He alone will do the milking while he is helped in the cultivation of his land by his wife e.g. breaking land, reaping, threshing.

The role of the wife is to tend to the water supply, cook and brew, make jugs and pots, cut soft grass for sleeping mats, thread beads and sew garments. It is she who has to tread daga, plaster hut walls and smear the floor with manure. She has to build the Chikwira (pot shelf) and the Chitukuriro (place where husband sits) she also grinds maize along with other household chores.

The Karanga children who are very respectful of their elders, are taught at an early age, depending on their sex, either the arts of hunting or housekeeping, e.g. boy at the age of 6 is a goat herder and entitled to a bachelor's hut and later herds cattle. The boys also concoct gum (urimbo) which is smeared on trees for catching birds. On the other hand girls are taught the secrets of cooking and maternal care. Both sexes help in cultivation and play games similar to European games.

The Karanga husband and wife have very little social intercourse, generally the wife waits on the husband and it is the main wife (Vahosi) who handles major household family matters. Generally two meals are eaten a day. The women and children are usually excluded from the convivial gathering of men.

Dzimbakwe, means the House of Sacred Stones, and it is thought the Acropolis was a meeting place of Gods and Ancestral Spirits who were contacted through intermediary of a medium. The Mwari is the oracular (it is thought the Acropolis contained an oracle) deity of the Karanga. The Mwari is the creator of the

physical world and comprises the conception of a trinity (Shovayehou - creator, Runji - preserver and Jaharumbi - interceder). Annual sacrifices are made to Mwari e.g. for the success of the crops. Usually a black ox is slaughtered. Mwari provides the feasts of nature and the fruits of the earth. He is served by an entourage of consecrated women. Mwari usually makes his will known by speaking from a cave. The Karanga also believe in a heaven (Denga) which houses ancestral spirits. There are four main spirits in the religion of the Karanga. These are:- (1) The Tribal Spirit - Mondoro - the monodoros are spirits of ancestral chiefs and tribal dignitaries. They manifest themselves through their recognised mediums (swikiros - true mediums are those who can drink and retain the warm blood of a sacrificial animal). These spirits watch over the interests of the whole community. (2) The Family Spirit - Midzimu - this spirit constitutes the "true domestic tutelary deities of the family." Everything that happens to the family is ascribed to a direct act of the midzimu. It is of utmost importance not to upset this spirit and sacrifices are made to it by the head of the family (a wife cannot take part in sacrifices to her husband's midzimu as it is not of her family.) (3) The Avenging or Retributory Spirit - Ngozi - this is the spirit of one who has been murdered or injured and the person who committed the deed has remained unpunished or unredressed, the person or his or her family will be visited by the Ngozi, who will cause sickness or even death, this will continue until the wrong has been atoned. (4) The Homeless or Alien Spirit - Shavi. (a) The Alien Shavi enters a medium who while possessed will speak the Shavi's language - it is at all times necessary to remain on the best of terms with this spirit. (b) The Personal Genius Shavi e.g. hunter, dancer - this Shavi effects individuals with its arts and must not be offended.

The Karanga people have a belief that "no man liveth unto himself" - this explains their hospitality.

In ending I would like to slip in a few brief snippets of information. The Karanga Chief is entitled to a number of skins, e.g. leopards, lions, or tusks which the hunters have obtained. The chief is greeted by clapping in unison while ordinary courtesy demands a mutual salutation and food and shelter for visitors. To the Karanga the crocodile is a reptile to be feared and respected, this may be the reason for its appearance on the pedestal holding the Zimbabwe bird. The colour green, on cloth for example, is supposed to be sacred to the Karanga as it gives life and fertility. The mbidziro (beer pot) has a number of necks to it and the Karanga considered it an honour to be allowed to drink from the mbidziro of a headman or nganga by means of a thin cane. Beer is used in all the Karangas social and economic celebrations - especially in religious ceremonies where it is considered a ceremonial beverage and is used freely - it can be said that the Karanga really enjoys practising his religion.

M.DAVIDSON, VI M.

ARCHITECTURE AT ZIMBABWE.

There are three main types of walling to be found in the ruins at Zimbabwe. These three types have been categorized as 'P', 'Q' and 'R' and are distinguished not by any particular styles, but more by the amount of care and skill that is apparent in the construction.

The most unskilled and careless type then is 'R' type which appears to have been built on a system where the courses were laid, and then secured and tightened by means of wedges and bits of rock pushed into cracks. The courses themselves are not, of course, at all straight or very evident.

The next step up is 'P' type, which is neater, but not very organised. Attempts at courses are evident, but these fade and run into one another haphazardly. The stones themselves, in both these types, are not finished in a particularly artistic fashion.

The 'Q' type is the most sophisticated with the stones finished very smoothly and even courses evident for long stretches. This type is in greatest evidence in the Great Enclosure, while the other two are to be found chiefly on the Acropolis and among the Valley Ruins.

S.REYNOLDS. U VI.

A CLASSIFICATION OF THE POTTERY FOUND AT ZIMBABWE.

The presence of pottery from lands other than Africa is important in showing that the inhabitants of Zimbabwe either traded with the people of these other lands or both had trade relations with a third country. This pottery is also very valuable for Carbon 14 dating purposes.

At the Zimbabwe Ruins the faience that has been found is mainly of Persian origin and appears to date from as early as the 13th and 14th centuries. One such piece found had the date and month marked on it but unfortunately the piece inscribed with the year has not been found. These Persian vessels were painted with rich colours - blue and green - within and were coated with a metallic lustre outside.

At other ruins in Rhodesia, notably Dhlo-Dhlo, most of the pottery found has been Chinese porcelain, dating from the middle Ming dynasty - about early 16th century - which hints at a different trade route.

The earthenware pottery present appears to have been made locally and can be classified into two types. (1) There is rough unornamented household pottery, hand-made and varnished with plumbago - similar to the hand-made pottery used by the semi-primitive African of to-day. (2) The other form of pottery is wheel made, unvarnished but ornamented with incised geometrical patterns. This is inferior in style to the pottery found at other ruins and may be attributed to the fact that the inhabitants of Zimbabwe made these incisions with a pointed stick while the clay was still wet. On the other hand, the incisions in pottery from other centres had been made with a stone flake, the day after baking.

P.LARK. C.I.

ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN GERMANY.

Between 1871 and 1914 Germany underwent a remarkable development in her economy which established her, by 1914, as the leading industrial nation in Europe. Germany in fact became a country of factories and big cities: a process which transformed the country completely.

Quite apart from the financial situation, political conditions in Germany were not very favourable for industrialisation. But during the economic transformation of Europe, Germany was one of the areas quite seriously effected. Like Belgium, she was rich in coal resources and the existence of thousand of tiny establishments gave her a long tradition and experience in the working of metals from the Hertz Mountains. However not much attempt was made to exploit the coal-fields in the Ruhr and the Saar until after 1815. Obviously with these and other coalfields, Germany had a good lead over other countries in Europe. With the set up in 1821 of the Gewerbe Institute - an institute of trades - trade was encouraged. This, with the services of British technicians, helped to foster the development of machines in factories, but in Berlin itself the lack of coal nearly made progress slow, and in the rest of the confederation insufficiency of capital and the confusion of frontiers and local laws hampered any speedy development. In the Rhine provinces the firms of Krupp at Essen, Haniel, Huyssen and Jacobi at Ruhrst and Oberhauser were indications of a greater power to come but these were very early days for German industry.

The greatly increased volume of goods circulating within Europe naturally demanded sound communications and the third characteristic of this period of economic transformation was a revolution in transport. Even before the railway age, striking improvements had been made in the use of roads, canals and rivers. However in Germany the local river tolls continued to be a hindrance to trade until 1834 when the invention of the steamboat overcame some of the physical difficulties making it possible as early as the 1820's to run services on the Rhine, the Weser and the Elbe.

In 1839 the first Hamburg steamship company was founded at a time when that city was the home port of 300 sailing ships totalling some 60,000 gross registered tons, by 1912 they were close on to 14,000 ships totalling 17 million tons registered in Hamburg, almost all of them were steamships whose carrying capacity was estimated as being four times that of the old sailing ships. At the same time, there was a major increase in the speed of communications: Benjamin Franklin's voyage to Europe took six weeks. The Savanna took 26 days for the crossing and shortly before World War I, fast steamships crossed the Atlantic in five days setting a standard which still remains unchallenged.

It was of course the Railways that were to bring the real revolution in Europe in communications. In early times of the German railway system the journey by rail from Frankfurt to Stuttgart would take 40 hours including stoppages (it takes 2 hours to-day).

Nonsensical customs barriers between German States were frequent, a fact pointed out later by economist Werner Sombart in his fine history of the German economy in the 19th century, when he wrote "often enough, there was no desire to improve communications. It

was thought desirable that stage coaches and freight trains should make slow progress so that the innkeepers and craftsmen of the area should profit from them as much as possible." All this changed and the first German Railway line from Nuremberg to Furth was built. By 1850 there were 3,625 miles of railway lines in Germany. As early as 1856 there were through lines from Kiel on the Baltic to Basle on the Swiss frontier, from Aachen via Cologne and Nuremberg. In 1841 August Baur built the first German locomotive in Berlin and by 1875 his enterprise was the biggest locomotive factory in the world. There were similar developments in the shipping trade.

It was not until the last third of the 19th century that industrialisation really got into its stride in Germany, e.g. in 1851 there were telephone exchanges in only seven German cities (about 1,500 telephones) while by 1910 telephone communications existed in 55,665 places and there were more than a million subscribers. Also during this period technical development emerged which was to form the basis of vital new branches of industry.

In 1866 Werner Von Siemens, the pioneer of power engineering invented the dynamo. In 1879 he built the world's first electric railway and the first electric train. The "Siemens-master Process" of steel making was developed by his brother.

Steel production grew enormously throughout the century, particularly after the adoption of the process developed by Bessmer and Thomas in England. Something new was added in 1880 when the Mannesman brothers began manufacturing seamless steel pipes. From 1870 on Karl von Linde laid the foundations of modern refrigeration techniques. In 1882, Oskar von Muller, who for a long time worked with Eric Rattena the founder of the "Allegeine Electricitats - Gesellschaft" discovered a method of a long distance power transmission.

From 1880 onward, a number of new inventions added to the new dimension of the Industrial Revolution. N.A.Ottowas the first in the internal combustion field in 1862 but was followed by Daimler in 1877, Benz in 1878 and Diesel in 1890, all of whom developed their own version of the combustion engine, while Robert Bosch was on the scene in 1886 with the first of the electrical equipment he invented for the new type of vehicle - the automobile. All these developments were also important for thermodynamics expert Hugo Junkers, who built the first all metal aeroplane in 1915, the starting point for many famous commercial aircraft.

Industry and trade continued to flourish and by 1914 Germany was well in the lead in coal, iron and steel production.

Figures show millions of metric tons

	1850	1870	1900	1914
<u>Coal Production</u>				
Germany	6	34	149	277
France	5	13.3	33.4	40
U.K.	57	112	228	292
<u>Iron Production</u>				
Germany	0.0	1.3	7.5	14.7
France	0.5	1.6	2.7	4.6
U.K.	2.2	6	9	11
<u>Steel Production</u>				
Germany	0.0	0.3	6.7	14
France	0.0	0.3	1.6	3.5
U.K.	0.0	0.7	5	6.5

This essay won the History Society Senior Essay Prize.

"ZIMBABWE : A RHODESIAN MYSTERY : EXAMINE THE EVIDENCE AS
TO THE CONSTRUCTION AND FUNCTION."

One century ago, in 1868, Adam Reander is said to have visited what has today become one of the world's foremost mysteries - the Great Zimbabwe Ruins. No one except the most insensitive can view these imposing relics of an unknown age without feeling awed by the grandeur, and an atmosphere of jealously guarded secrets; without asking questions which lead to further questions, with the final answer seeming continually to be drifting further and further into the obscure mists of age. Who built these ruins? Why did they build them? When did they build them? Where did the builders come from? In the ever increasing search for answers to these questions, a controversy has arisen, which today still leads to inconclusive arguments and renewed research.

There are at present, two main schools of thought concerning this mystery - the "mediaevalist" and the "ancients or antiquarians." This last is the older, and has long been the more favoured. It is the school which supports the theory of Phoenician origin for the ruins, and has mentioned connections with Solomon and Sheba. The connections with Solomon and Sheba are probably due to the conclusions of the early Arabs. When Arab traders saw deserted buildings or mine-workings in the heart of Africa they would naturally ascribe these apparently ancient places to their folk-lore hero, Solomon. It was different with the Portuguese chroniclers, most of whom knew nothing of Arab folk-lore and were ready to believe almost any tale about the new lands, so over-credulity led later Portuguese writers to bring Solomon into the picture, and with his name was linked that of the Queen of Sheba.

The leaders of this first school of thought, besides the Portuguese, would appear to be two Germans - a missionary, the Reverend Merensky, and a geologist, Karl Mauch who in 1870 rediscovered Zimbabwe. They are supported by Thomas Baines, Theodore Bent, R.N.Swan, R.N.Hall and W.G.Neal, amongst many others. The arguments which these people use in support of their theories are thus.

Firstly, the questions were asked: Do the stone structures bear any relation to the architectural methods of any ancient nation? and which nation had all the necessary architectural ability in the field of stone masonry, and the necessary mining and agricultural knowledge, trade experience, maritime power, labour resources, industry, toughness and fearlessness to build and mine and worship on the scale on which the ancients did in the area of the Zimbabwe's.

From what is left of Phoenician architecture, it is known that the Phoenicians built in stone without cement, and that they built the walls of their cities from huge blocks of stone roughly fashioned. According to Renan, the distinguishing feature of Phoenician architecture was its massive and imposing strength "a want indeed of finish in details, but a general effect of power and grandeur. In short, it is monolithic art." Moreover, Rawlinson says that the Phoenicians "laid their courses horizontally in colossal blocks, rough hewn in the main, but smoother and carefully bevelled at the edges . ." Renan also refers to a Phoenician wall erected "upon the outermost ranges of the rocks in such a way as to impend over tolerably deep water. (a parallel

is drawn between this and the massive wall of the Acropolis on Zimbabwe Hill right on the edge of an eighty to ninety foot precipice). It is composed of quadrangular prisms nine feet three inches in height and from thirteen to sixteen feet long. (Here immediately is a flaw in the argument for the stone at Zimbabwe measure not more than about eight inches by ten) sometimes without art and even with a sort of strange negligence, the joints of the stones being in some cases exactly imposed one over the other. The courses are at times regular, small blocks being used to fill in apertures, and a perfect junction of the parts being in this way effected, but at times the arrangement of the blocks is without any strict or rigorous order, with the exception that they are always laid horizontally." He also brings to notice that the stones are made of material from the immediate neighbourhood, as are those of Zimbabwe and that the rock was obtained in much the same way.

Another argument in favour of this interpretation is that enough is known of the religion, industry, organizing ability and general ability of the builders of Zimbabwe to identify them as the Phoenicians.

Similarities are also drawn between small terra cotta figurines found in Cyprus, and soapstone carvings found in Rhodesia, mainly in facial expression, this expression being definitely non-negro.

It is also said that at the time that the walls were built and the gold was mined, the only people capable of undertaking these enterprises were the Phoenicians, and that the Bantu tribes have to this day not reached that stage of development, tribal enterprise being a local affair not including gold-mining, scientific dry-packing with prepared stone blocks, drained walls, or terraced irrigation farming, nor the scientific construction of conical towers, the carving of soapstone stelae, the decoration of walls with a double chevron pattern, the carving of plain or decorated phalli and other emblems of nature worship.

Evidence is also given of a Byblos coin which bears a Greek inscription and depicts a conical tower.

Another argument is that several of the Portuguese historians describe the buildings of the Great Zimbabwe as ruins at their time in the late sixteenth and seventeenth century. Thus they cannot have been built by the Bantu as some investigators think, for the Bantu invasions had only recently arrived in that neighbourhood.

J.T. Bent prefaces the third edition of his book on his excavations and explorations in Rhodesia in 1891 by quoting from Professor D.H. Muller, the great authority on Southern Arabian archaeology, who wrote that "Marib, the Mariaba of Greek and Roman geographers, was the capital of the old Sabaeen Kingdom of Southern Arabia, East North East of Marib, half-an-hour's ride brings one to the ruin called by the Arabs the Houram of Bilkis or the Queen of Sheba. It is an elliptical building with a circuit of three hundred feet and shows a remarkable likeness to the great circular temple at Zimbabwe." This led Bent to conclude that it is highly probable that the temple at Zimbabwe was in fact originally a Sabaeen temple as the points of comparison are so strong and there is also a strong

connection between the star-worshipping Sabaeans and the temple with its points orientated towards the sun. He also says that from the curves and orientation of Zimbabwe and other Mashonaland ruins it can safely be considered that their builders possessed knowledge of geometry and the heavens. He says that nothing further can be proved, but it is confirmatory evidence that the builders were of a Semitic race and Arabian origin and excludes the possibility of any negroid race having had more to do with their construction than as the slaves of a higher civilization.

Bent also sees connections and similarities between designs of the Egyptian Hawk and the Zimbabwe bird and also finds traces of connections with Phoenician, Assyrian and Hittitic styles and symbols in other finds.

Arguments are also put forward with regard to burials and graves. The following extracts from Hall and Neale describe the burials of people whose skeletons were excavated from underneath the granite cement floors found within the walls of some of the Rhodesian Ruins - not the skeletons of Bantu found buried a few feet below the surface in the midden heaps inside or outside the ruins. "Not one of the forty skeletal remains of ancients has been discovered without a necklace of (gold) beads . . . The beads vary in size and weight and are all of solid gold . . . Some of the larger beads had the Chevron and other Zimbabwe patterns neatly engraved on them, and on some the engraving is so fine that it can only be discovered with the aid of a magnifying glass. (It is here pointed out that the Phoenicians were top rank engravers. Moreover, Rawlinson says that gold beads were generally worn by Phoenicians of Europe before 500 B.C.).

"The ancients found in the ruins are buried at full length and always either on the right or left side . . . The mediaeval and modern kaffir peoples were buried near the surface and many feet above those of the ancients, between whom there were always cemented floors and several feet of soil. (These features concerning burial were noticed of remains found at Mapungubwe not at Great Zimbabwe).

With regard to the Chevron patterning, it is said that these are meant to represent something "nearest the hearts of the Phoenicians, namely the stylized version of the waves they loved so much, the waves that brought them immortal fame - only doubled this time."

These are the main arguments put forward by those in favour of the theory of Phoenician origin. The principal leaders of the Mediaevalists are Professor David Randall-MacIver, Doctor Gertrude Caton-Thompson and Roger Summers. This theory is the more modern of the two and is gradually replacing the other one, although this last is at the moment apparently the generally established and accepted theory. Both MacIver and Miss Caton-Thompson were trained Egyptologists, and therefore, according to Summers well suited to tackling the problem.

After his examination of the ruins, MacIver came to the conclusion that Hall was in error, and wrote "Though the mistake is a pardonable one, considering the deceptive appearance of the section" (a section excavated by Hall in Enclosure 15 of the Great Enclosure) "It certainly does show stratification only it is the stratification resulting from the procedure adopted in building piecemeal such a tiered platform as that which supported the Chief's hut at Natatali."

MacIver goes on to point out that below the daga mass was a mixture of sand and ashes where there were spindle whorls, coils of copper wire for bracelets, and household pottery, both plain and decorated. That is to say "exactly the same objects which were found in the top surface 3.30m higher. The pottery from this lowest level is that which Mr. Hall calls Makalanga, and which is, in fact, exactly like modern Kaffir pottery." MacIver then proceeds to the conclusion "It is impossible, therefore, to resist the conclusion that the people who inhabited the 'Elliptical Temple' when it was built belonged to tribes whose arts and manufactures were indistinguishable from those of the modern Makalanga." Putting all the evidence together, MacIver on the last page of his book gives the opinion that the huts and their surrounding walls "are unquestionably African in every detail, and belong to a period which is fixed by foreign imports as in general mediaeval." He considers that the importance of Zimbabwe centred around the sixteenth century A.D. with the earliest possible date for any of its buildings about two hundred years earlier. He admitted the possibility of a slightly earlier settlement and considered that by the seventeenth century Zimbabwe had lost its importance and was decaying to be finally ruined by some unrecorded invasion of savage tribes between the seventeenth and nineteenth centuries.

In 1929, Miss Gertrude Caton-Thompson made a thorough examination of the ruins and reached conclusions similar to those of MacIver. She believed its original foundation to have belonged to the eighth or ninth centuries A.D. and its full occupation to the thirteenth century, the earlier dates being determined by beads and later by Chinese porcelain. On the question of origin, she came to a definite conclusion. She said "without over-rating the security of my findings I have stated the results of my excavations: examination of all the existing evidence, gathered from every quarter, still can produce not one single item that is not in accordance with the claim of Bantu origin and mediaeval date."

In 1958 Robinson dug a wide deep trench right through the mass of daga in the Western Enclosure of the Acropolis, and discovered a series of twelve floors and several sets of hut walls lying one on top of another. In other test trenches he found deposits obviously older than those in the main trench, and therefore now had sections covering the whole period during which the Acropolis was occupied. A summary of Robinson's description of his sections is as follows:- The top fifteen inches contained pottery which is so recent that it can be found even today in surrounding Karanga villages. Beneath this was a hard layer which protected those which lay below from rain wash. This deposit contained pottery similar to that from Khami and other ruins as well as glass beads of various colours and pieces of copper wire. Part of two hut walls also appeared. Beneath this was a good depth of reddish daga in which were found a good many hut floors, remains of walls and so on. Here also was a different pottery from that of deposit above and rather different glass beads. Right at the bottom, almost on bed rock was a layer of broken up hut walls under which lay ashes containing yet another type of pottery. Finally came a layer of washed down granite sand and beneath that a layer containing yet another and completely different pottery.

The conclusion drawn from this was that there were five phases of occupation on the Acropolis. In the Great Enclosure, however,

trenches dug by Whitty and Summers revealed a different picture. Nearly all the pottery belonged to one type, namely, phase IV (the last but one) of that found on the Acropolis. Also disclosed were various daga sequences which indicated destroyed huts and their relative ages.

As well as examining the daga sequences, Whitty examined the walling and formulated a classification of walling styles - P type, Q type (recognized as the better and neater type) and R type, very rough. He also recognized a class PQ, which not only appeared to be intermediate between P and Q on stylistic grounds, but proved to be a transitional type. Whitty demonstrated that the sequence of walls was P - PQ - Q, a sequence which was proved by the stratigraphy of the coloured daga sequences already mentioned.

Summers puts forward three possibilities for the builders of the ruins. Firstly, there is the balembe who are exceptionally good craftsmen in iron, bronze and pottery, have no chiefs, and live as "strangers within the gates of the tribes which patronize them." Recently these people have claimed that their forefathers built Zimbabwe, a claim which deserves consideration on grounds of technical ability. However, Zimbabwe building problems were administrative as well as technical, and it is debatable how well the Lumba would have coped with matters of organization in which nowadays they seem so unskilled.

Although the theory of the Rozwi having built the structure has not much support, it is now known that the Rozwi were fine organizers with ability to weld together small groups. They were also very great magicians and were capable of providing a sufficiently powerful religious or "magical" stimulus for the erection of Zimbabwe's most important buildings. The Rozwi were small in number, and although they may not have done any actual building, it is easy to imagine them directing others more craftsmanlike than themselves.

There is most evidence to support the theory of Shona origin. The ancestors of the Shona, especially the Karanga, are believed to have been very early migrants into Rhodesia and to have been responsible for much of the actual gold mining in this country. They were, therefore sufficiently advanced technically to have tackled stone buildings. Also, the country of Monomotapa is always called by the Portuguese "Mocaranga" or Karangaland. This too, is the name by which the Angoni invaders knew it over a century ago. Finally, all the early stone buildings are in the old Karanga areas of the country.

It is impossible to be very certain as to the identity of the builders, so we may merely suppose that the Shona (possibly the Karanga) are likely to have had a large hand in the beginning of the work, while perhaps the Lemba may have followed and improved the building technique.

Here then, is a rough outline of the evidence supporting the theory of Bantu origin, and considering each theory and the evidence in support of each, it is not very difficult to decide which of the two is the more reasonable and likely. The argument of the supporters of the Phoenician theory is very weak, and at no stage is it based on sound, complete material basis. In drawing their conclusions, these people have considered only those features

which in some way support their theory and have, as far as I can see, conveniently ignored those features which do not. Their arguments are in no way conclusive, and in many cases the evidence seems to have been adopted to suit their theory. Take for instance the question of walling. The "Ancients" ignore Whitty's classification of walling, and the transition from P to EQ to Q which indicates that the original builders discovered and developed this building technique for themselves. As already mentioned, the stones, used by the Phoenicians are very much larger than those used at Zimbabwe. Moreover, the "Ancients" ignore the fact that there are huts within the walls known to be as old as the walls themselves and also many of the walls have obviously been built around and between huts. That is, they have been built to accommodate huts. No evidence has so far been produced to indicate that the Phoenicians lived in huts. A similarity has been drawn between the elliptical "Temple" and some buildings in North Africa. However, there is no Phoenician equivalent of the Acropolis which is known to have been inhabited earlier than the "temple," (judging from the five phases of pottery). At no stage have I seen descriptions of sections and trenches which provide evidence in support of the Phoenician theory, whereas the "Mediaevalists" have produced many such descriptions.

Not only did the Phoenicians not live in huts, but they did not make African pottery, and yet such pottery has been found at the very earliest stages of the Acropolis.

With regard to the statement that judging from the nature and position of the buildings (they are facing the sun) the builders must have had some knowledge of geometry and the heavens, who is to say that this was not because of some feature of another religion, not necessarily the Phoenician star-worshippers.

Having decided who built the structures, one must decide why they were built. The "Mediaevalists" say that it was undoubtedly a religious centre and that all the buildings on the Hill and in the valley were put there because of the special sanctity of the site. Some were royal dwellings, others administrative buildings, but they crowded round the sacred area just as King, Parliament, Government and trade around the Royal Church of Westminster Abbey. The Acropolis may have been the special quarters of the King and priests, while the valley buildings may have been the headquarters of the centralized administration which we know that the Monomotapa kings and later the Rozwi Mambos maintained "In other words, Zimbabwe was, as MacIver, pointed out over half a century ago the old Monomotapan capital."

To sum up, then, Zimbabwe, would seem to have been an ancient sacred site, connected with an autochthonous religion which even today has very many devotees. The nature of the rocks of the surrounding hills provided suitable stone for building, the technique of building roughly-coursed stone walls was introduced and may be invented. The earliest walls surrounded sacred sites on the Hill. "To this ancient sacred place there naturally gravitated local rulers and Zimbabwe became the Metropolis of a large confederacy under Kings whose dynastic name was Monomotapa (or more probably, Mwene wa tapa). Later this dynasty was replaced by the Rozwi Mambos, whose chief contribution to Zimbabwe was a series of immense walls built with a greatly improved technique. Throughout this time, Zimbabwe was an immensely wealthy place, drawing to itself nearly the whole income from a very lucrative

trade in gold and ivory conducted mainly with Arabs and partly with Portuguese." It has also been suggested as the ruins lie on a trade route from Sofala to the interior, they could have been built as one of a series of forts to protect this route.

In spite of all the evidence, or perhaps because of the conflicting evidence, we can so far only make guesses as to the builders of, and function of, the Great Zimbabwe ruins. The ruins have long fascinated many people, and being typically Rhodesian, are one of the greatest prides of the country. There are still many questions to be answered and many problems to be solved, something which may never quite be achieved. As Summers says, one may perhaps change the famous words of Pliny a little to read "Ex Zimbabwe semper aliquid novum" or as one of the antiquarians said in criticism of Summers "out of Zimbabwe always something black."

C. MURRAY U VI.

BOOK REVIEWS.

LIFE IN GEORGIAN ENGLAND - E.N. Williams.
(Published 1963 : B.T. Batsford, Ltd. Eng.
G.P. Putnam & Sons. U.S.A.)

This book deals generally with life in Georgian England and it divides England into its social classes.

The opening chapter, "The English People" deals very generally with several aspects of life at the very beginning of the eighteenth century and is really concentrated on providing a background and reasons for the changes which were, later, to come about. Filled with figures, this chapter is able to provide details only on a few subjects, e.g. population, while merely mentioning others.

The rest of the book is divided into upper, middle and lower classes and deals with the change which overcomes them. The chapter on the middle class is excellent and gives a really good idea of middle class life at this time. Upper class life is treated by taking particular families, mainly and gives a good picture of only the men at this time. In fact, the book deals mainly with men and gives very little space to the activities of the women.

Williams, however, conveys a very clear picture of the life and ideas which were accepted. His section on the working and living conditions of the lower classes is very good and indicates what could be accepted as a "true" picture of their life.

He also deals with the cultural aspect of this age and, followed by his concluding chapter, it is relatively easy to follow the modes and ideas which passed through Georgian hands, changing from relatively loose morals to those approaching Victorian ideas, from logic and reason in thought and writing to romanticism.

The book gives an excellent idea of life in Georgian times and would serve excellently as a background book to this period. However, it is too brief and too general for more detailed use. It is very well illustrated and the plates in the book give additional stronger impressions of conditions. Unfortunately, in attempting to cover such a wide period in so small a book, Williams had had to use a fairly cramped style of writing which makes the book at times, both hard to read and uninteresting. Despite this, it is well worth using for background knowledge of the Georgian era.

F. GARSIDE U VI.

'KING CHOLERA - THE BIOGRAPHY OF A DISEASE - Norman Longmate
(Published by Hamish Hamilton).

This is indeed, if I may stretch a point, a rare "work of art" in the study of a disease that has itself become rare in our society of to-day.

For this book so clearly portrays the horrors and agonies of a death-bearing disease, whose mere name only a century ago was enough to cause whole towns to empty in terror, and to arouse a fear in the people of Britain, that the pestilence sweeping the country might prove as destructive as the Black Death and Great Plague had been to earlier centuries.

The book, however is not a mere objective narration of the arrival of this disease to the exclusion of all other momentous, contemporary occurrences, but rather sets out to show as well - and as such proves invaluable as a guide to English social and political history throughout a large part of the nineteenth century - how 'cholera' between its first arrival in 1831 and its last serious assault in 1866, attacked almost every corner of the kingdom, leaving its mark upon British history at many points.

It gives a clear insight into the contemporary society, particularly the lower and middle strata, as these were the worst effected areas. It shows how this "King Cholera" added a new and disturbing element to the agitation for the vote; how it brought a new horror to the Irish famine; how it helped to carry Florence Nightingale to the Crimea and make her a household name in the history of nursing; how it entwined itself intricately in the workings of English politics - indeed in 1855 it became one of the main issues, contributing to Lord Palmerston's rise to power as Prime Minister, and it was later to cause this same to be accused of atheism, a grave sin indeed, in times such as they were, when Christianity experienced a marked rise in support in the hope of appeasing God, and therefore the pestilence.

But most of all the book depicts skilfully how the outbreak of cholera demonstrated the need for state control of housing standards, for a system of medical help for the poor and a public health service (noticeably during this period were passed the "Poor Law" of 1834 and the Public Health Act, two major breakthroughs, paving the way for the Welfare State of our own day).

In "King Cholera" Norman Longmate vividly recreates the bewilderment, ingenuity and courage of men and women faced with a challenge beyond their experience and comprehension - in short an important contribution to social history, invaluable to a student of English history, and a book which I thoroughly recommend to be read.

G.RIMMER U VI.

CULTURE AND SOCIETY IN NINETEENTH CENTURY EUROPE. VOLUME SIXTH, 1967.

Although being a comprehensive survey of nineteenth century Europe, this book does tend to be irrelevant in places. We first get a detailed account of the rational movements which broke out throughout the continent and the way in which romanticism influenced them. This is an extremely important chapter as this was a predominant factor in the shaping of "culture and society in 19th century Europe."

Realism and classicism and their effect on literature and art are also discussed in this chapter, with interesting theories from famous men such as Nietzsche, Schlegel and Hegel.

Socialism, which is today one of the most powerful political forces in the world, is also discussed from the very beginning of its doctrine (Saint-Simon and Fourier) to Owenism, and from then on, the first anticapitalist writers to Marxism and finally Communism. Industrialism is also included in this chapter and the link between the two is well illustrated. It is very apt that they should be included in the same chapter, as they are possibly the two most dominant factors in Europe in the nineteenth century in affecting culture and society.

After this chapter, the literatures of the main countries in Europe are closely examined, but I feel that this fails to produce a full enough picture of culture and society, with the exception of such writings as those of Balzac.

Nevertheless, the developments in Europe in the fields of science, literature, industrialism and society in general are brought out very well.

I. PALFRAMAN U VI.

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I would like to take this opportunity to thank all those who have assisted the Society this year, particularly speakers at meetings, and parents who made the Zimbabwe trip a reality, and secondly to Mrs. Cox and Mr. Forsyth without whom this magazine would not have materialised.

P. LARK (Editor)

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